
**SAFEGUARDING PUBLIC HEALTH: ASSESSMENT OF WATER QUALITY
AND POTABILITY OF WATER SOURCES IN
SITIO MAMPUENG, OLONGAPO CITY**

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ABSTRACT

Ensuring safe drinking water is crucial for maintaining human health and well-being. This study assesses the water quality and potability of water sources in Sitio Mampung, Olongapo City, to determine their safety for human consumption. Water samples from a spring and a water reservoir were tested for key parameters, including Total Coliform, Fecal Coliform, Heterotrophic Plate Counts, Turbidity, Total Dissolved Solids, Iron Total, Hardness Total, and pH levels, in accordance with the 2017 Philippine National Standards for Drinking Water (PNSDW). Results revealed that while the water sources met physico-chemical standards, they failed microbiological tests. Specifically, levels of Total Coliform, Fecal Coliform, and Heterotrophic Plate Count significantly exceeded allowable limits, indicating potential fecal contamination. The spring water also exceeded turbidity standards, although both sources were within acceptable limits for Total Dissolved Solids, Iron, Hardness, and pH. The findings highlight the non-potable status of the water, posing serious health risks to residents. The study recommends immediate implementation of protective measures, water treatment, and community education to improve water quality and public health. This research contributes to the broader goal of advancing Sustainable Development Goal 6 by promoting access to clean and safe water, thereby supporting sustainable water resource management and reducing waterborne diseases.

Keywords: *water quality assessment, potable water, public health, Sitio Mampung*

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INTRODUCTION

Ensuring safe drinking water is crucial for maintaining human health and well-being. In the Philippines, like many other countries, inadequate water quality poses significant risks, leading to a rise in waterborne diseases such as cholera, diarrhea, and typhoid

fever, as reported by the Department of Health Philippines (2019). These preventable health risks are worsened by insufficient water and sanitation services, which create vulnerabilities for individuals. Moreover, introducing toxic substances into aquatic ecosystems further threatens natural water sources, disrupting ecological balance and integrity. Collective action is necessary to address these challenges and safeguard our water resources, which are vital for human well-being and environmental sustainability. In the beautiful city of Olongapo, the community of Sitio Mampung heavily relies on its water quality. However, water sources in Sitio Mampung, situated in Barangay Old Cabalan, face threats from both natural factors and human activities, making them susceptible to pollution. Clean water is crucial for communities like Mampung, yet they remain vulnerable to water contamination without a comprehensive understanding of the health risks associated with water sources such as spring water and water reservoirs. Previous research by Escatron et al. (2022) has highlighted the dangers of water pollution and its implications for vital water sources like falls, rivers, wells, and poso (water pumps). There was already a project that addressed the need of clean potable water for the sitio itself by building a water tank reservoir (Asio et al., 2023; Asio et al., 2024) however, it is currently under maintenance.

The socio-economic disparities among Sitio Mampung residents present additional challenges in addressing water quality issues. Economic constraints hinder the establishment of essential infrastructure and services, such as water supply systems and sanitation facilities, forcing communities to rely on inadequately monitored and treated water sources. This exposes them to contracting diseases and other health problems, as documented in the *Journal of Environmental Science* in 2012. Without effective treatment and distribution of water sources, the community faces threats of disease outbreaks and adverse health effects.

Access to clean potable water is crucial for preventing waterborne diseases and sustaining good health, as emphasized by the World Health Organization (2022). Therefore, conducting a water quality evaluation exercise in Mampung is imperative. It not only ensures the safety of its residents but also protects ecological integrity and informs decision-making regarding water resource management. Prioritizing water quality assessments, as advocated by Masangkay et al. (2020), is essential for addressing existing challenges and implementing sustainable solutions.

The UN SDG 6, or United Nations Sustainable Development Goal of Ensuring Availability and Sustainable Management of Water and Sanitation for All, is a key global goal established by UN-Water in collaboration with UNEP (UN Environmental Programme, 2021). This initiative aims to achieve sustainable and safe drinking water and sanitation for all, as one in three people currently live without proper sanitation, resulting in preventable disease and death. Although significant progress has been made with clean drinking water, the lack of sanitation undermines these advances (United Nations Organization, 2015). Unfortunately, the world is still far from reaching SDG 6, which may jeopardize the 2030 Agenda of Sustainable Development (UN-Water, 2021).

This research aims to contribute to advancing Sustainable Development Goal 6, which focuses on ensuring access to clean water and sanitation for all. The goal is to help achieve the Sustainable Development Goals and progress towards a sustainable future. Specifically, it aims to assess water quality to identify potential contaminants and propose measures and strategies for effective interventions. By pinpointing areas of concern and developing solutions, this research seeks to improve access to clean and safe water for consumption, promoting better health outcomes and environmental sustainability.

As mentioned, this study aims to assess the water quality and potability of water sources, specifically in Sitio Mampueng. It involves sampling and testing water from sources, including spring water and water reservoir. The analysis will cover microbiological, chemical, and physical characteristics in compliance with the 2017 Philippine National Standards for Drinking Water to guarantee drinking water's safety and high quality. Furthermore, the study will integrate local knowledge and engage stakeholders in ongoing conservation efforts to bridge the gap between research findings and practical interventions for sustainable environmental practices.

By critically appraising existing frameworks, the research aims to identify areas for improvement and opportunities for enhancing evidence-based policy recommendations and strategies. Ultimately, the findings of this research endeavor to inform both academia and practical interventions, fostering healthier and safer water consumption practices in Sitio Mampueng.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Sitio Mampueng, a remote Aeta community in Old Cabalan, Olongapo City. With approximately 200 families, the residents rely primarily on a water reservoir and a mountain spring for their daily water needs. Water samples were purposively collected from these two main sources.

The collected water samples were submitted to Subic Water and Sewerage Co., Inc. (SUBICWATER) for laboratory testing. SUBICWATER is an ISO-certified water and sewerage utility known for its adherence to standard water testing protocols. The analysis assessed both microbiological and physico-chemical parameters based on the 2017 Philippine National Standards for Drinking Water (PNSDW).

Microbiological parameters tested included Total Coliform, Fecal Coliform, and Heterotrophic Plate Count (HPC). Total and Fecal Coliform were analyzed using the Multiple-Tube Fermentation Technique, and results were reported in terms of Most Probable Number (MPN). The Heterotrophic Plate Count was determined through the Pour Plate Method to estimate the general population of bacteria present in the water.

For physico-chemical parameters, turbidity was measured using the Nephelometric Method. Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) were analyzed by drying samples at 180°C following Standard Method 2540C. The iron content of the water was determined using the Phenanthroline Method, while Total Hardness was measured through the EDTA

Titrimetric Method. Lastly, the pH level was assessed using the Electrometric Method with a calibrated pH meter.

Table 1. Standard Values for Microbiological and Physical-Chemical Quality for Acceptability Aspects of Drinking Water

Microbiological Quality	
Parameter	Standard Values
1. Total Coliform	<1.1 MPN (Most Probable Number)/ 100 mL
2. Fecal Coliform	<1.1 MPN (Most Probable Number)/ 100 mL
3. Heterotrophic Plate Count (HPC)	<500 CFU / mL
Physical–Chemical Quality	
Parameter	Maximum Allowable Level (MAL)
1. Turbidity	5 NTU
2. Total Hardness	300 mg / L
3. pH	6.6 – 8.5
4. Total Dissolved Solids	600 mg / L
5. Iron Total	1.0 mg / L

All test results were compared against the allowable limits and standard values set by the Philippine National Standards for Drinking Water (2017). Parameters were evaluated to determine compliance with potability guidelines for both microbiological and physico-chemical aspects. Findings were summarized in tables and interpreted descriptively to assess the safety of the water sources for community use.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Table 2 summarizes the water quality test results from the sample source water reservoir. The water samples underwent analysis at the SubicWater Freeport Water Laboratory for Physical and Chemical Analysis Tests. The parameters analyzed include Temperature, Total Dissolved Solids, Turbidity, Total Hardness, Total Iron, and pH.

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

Water has the ability to dissolve a variety of inorganic and organic minerals and salts such as potassium, calcium, sodium, bicarbonates, and more, which can result in an undesirable taste and a diluted appearance in the water's color (Meride & Ayenew, 2016). A high Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) value in water indicates a high level of mineralization. According to the Philippine National Standards for Drinking Water (PNSDW) 2017, the acceptable limit for Total Dissolved Solids is 600 mg/L. The TDS concentration of the water reservoir was measured at 145 mg/L, significantly below the permissible limit of 600 mg/L. This suggests a low level of dissolved substances in the water, indicating that it is relatively clean.

Table 2: Water Reservoir Physical and Chemical Analysis Test Report

SAMPLE SOURCE/ LOCATION	DATE & TIME OF COLLECTION	TEST PARAMETER (S)	UNIT (S)	METHODOLOGY	RESULT(S)	PERMISSIBLE LIMITS PNSDW 2017
PHYSICAL						
WATER RESERVOIR	Aug. 01, 2024	Total Dissolve Solids	mg/L	2540 C. Total Dissolve Solids Dried at 180 C	145	600
		Turbidity	NTU	2130 B. Nephelometric	2.56	5
CHEMICAL						
Sitio Mampueng, Old Cabalan	10:33 AM	Hardness Total	mg/L	2430 C. EDTA Titrimetric	67	300
		Iron Total	mg/L	3500 Fe. B. Phenanthroline	0.05	1
		pH		4500- H+ B. Electrometric	8.21	6.50 – 8.50

Turbidity

Materials such as clay, silt, tiny inorganic and organic matter, algae, and other microscopic organisms can lead to high turbidity in water, as explained by the U.S. Geological Survey (2019). The clarity of water is inversely related to its turbidity – the lower the turbidity, the clearer the water, and the higher the turbidity, the cloudier the water appears. When water has high turbidity, it indicates the presence of a greater number of particles. Excessive water turbidity is not only visually unappealing, but it can also pose health risks to those who consume it. Although the Philippine National Standards for Drinking Water (PNSDW) 2017 states that turbidity is not dangerous, elevated levels can still be a concern. In the water sample, the measured turbidity was 2.56 NTU, below the permissible limit of 5 NTU set by PNSDW 2017. This reading indicates clear water with minimal suspended particles.

Hardness, Total

The hardness of water refers to the combined concentration of both calcium and magnesium ions present in the water. Although total water hardness is generally not considered hazardous to human health, it can lead to plumbing and appliance issues due to scale buildup (Vermont Department of Health, 2018). With a total hardness of 67 mg/L, the water sample falls below the permissible limit of 300 mg/L. This indicates that the water is relatively low in hardness, making it suitable for various applications and safe to drink.

Iron, Total

Iron is a naturally occurring mineral. The safety of drinking water containing iron depends on the concentration and specific form of the mineral. According to Annem (2017), low

levels of iron in drinking water are generally safe and can even contribute to the necessary dietary intake of iron, which is essential for good health. However, high levels of iron in water can affect its taste, color, and safety.

In the water sample from the reservoir, the total iron concentration was measured at 0.05 mg/L, significantly below the permissible limit set by PNSDW 2017 of 1 mg/L. This indicates a low iron content in the water, well within the acceptable range.

pH

The pH scale spans from 0 to 14, with 7 representing neutrality. Any value below 7 indicates acidity, while any value above 7 indicates basicity. The pH level of water can influence its taste, corrosiveness, and suitability for different purposes. The pH of the water sample was 8.21, falling within the acceptable range of 6.50 to 8.50, as specified by the PNSDW 2017.

Table 3: Spring Water Physical and Chemical Analysis Test Report

SAMPLE SOURCE/ LOCATION	DATE & TIME OF COLLECTION	TEST PARAMETER (S)	UNIT (S)	METHODOLOGY	RESULT(S)	PERMISSIBLE LIMITS PNSDW 2017
PHYSICAL						
SPRING WATER	Aug. 01, 2024	Total Dissolve Solids	mg/L	2540 C. Total Dissolve Solids Dried at 180 C	100	600
		Turbidity	NTU	2130 B. Nephelometric	10.68	5
		CHEMICAL				
Sitio Mampueng, Old Cabalan	10:14 AM	Hardness Total	mg/L	2430 C. EDTA Titrimetric	30	300
		Iron Total	mg/L	3500 Fe. B. Phenanthroline	0.29	1
		pH		4500- H+ B. Electrometric	7.71	6.50 – 8.50

Table 3 summarizes the water quality test results from the sample source, spring water. The water samples underwent analysis at the SubicWater Freeport Water Laboratory for Physical and Chemical Analysis Tests. The parameters analyzed include Temperature, Total Dissolved Solids, Turbidity, Total Hardness, Total Iron, and pH.

Total Dissolved Solids

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) refers to the concentration of minerals, metals, organic materials, and salts dissolved in a specific volume of water. The allowable limit of TDS in water is 600 mg/L according to the 2017 Philippine National Standard for Drinking Water. The result shows that spring water has a TDS level of 100 mg/L, which falls well within the 600 mg/L threshold set by the PNSDW 2017. A low TDS value indicates high water

quality, suggesting a lower presence of dissolved minerals and salts, resulting in a more pleasant taste of the water.

Turbidity

Turbidity is the presence of suspended particles in water. Measuring turbidity allows for visual evaluation (Magwilang et al., 2023). Water samples collected during the dry season appear clear, whereas during the wet season, they are mostly turbid. The measured turbidity of the water is 10.68 NTU, which exceeds the 2017 PNSDW limit of 5 NTU. Elevated turbidity levels can indicate the presence of suspended particles, which may harbor harmful microorganisms and reduce water clarity, potentially rendering the water unsafe without additional treatment.

Hardness, Total

The total hardness of water is determined by the concentration of calcium and magnesium salts. According to the PNSDW, the maximum permissible limit for this parameter is 300 mg/L. The test results indicate a concentration of 30 mg/L, which falls into the category of low hardness, below the allowable limit of 300 mg/L specified in PNSDW 2017. This level suggests that the water is classified as soft due to its relatively low levels of calcium and magnesium ions.

Iron, Total

The PNSDW 2017 establishes a maximum permissible limit for iron in drinking water at 0.3 milligrams per liter (mg/L). This means that the concentration of iron in potable water should not exceed this limit. In the water sample, specifically spring water, the iron content is 0.29 mg/L, which falls below the PNSDW 2017 limit of 0.3 mg/L. This low level of iron suggests that the water is unlikely to cause staining or a metallic taste, making it more suitable for consumption and household use.

pH

The pH value of water is an indicator of its acidity or alkalinity. The generally acceptable pH range for drinking water is between 6.5 to 8.5. According to the test result, Spring water has a pH of 7.71, which falls within the recommended range of 6.50 to 8.50 (PNSDW 2017). This pH level, which indicates a slightly alkaline to neutral nature, suggests that the water is chemically balanced, reducing the risk of corrosion or scaling in distribution systems.

Table 4 summarizes the microbiological water quality results of spring water and reservoir samples from Sitio Mampueng, Old Cabalan, analyzed by the SubicWater Freeport Water Laboratory. The parameters tested were Heterotrophic Plate Count (HPC), Total Coliforms, and Fecal Coliforms.

Table 4: Spring Water and Water Reservoir Microbiological Analysis Test Report

SAMPLE IDENTIFICATION	HPC (CFU/ml)	RESULT OF ANALYSIS (MPN/100ml)		REMARKS
		COLIFORM		
		Total	Fecal	
Spring Water	30	>8.0	>8.0	Failed
Water Reservoir	>6500	>8.0	>8.0	Failed

Note: PNSDW 2017 LIMIT:

Total Coliform <1.1 MPN/100ml

Fecal Coliform <1.1 MPN/100ml

Heterotrophic Plate Count <500 CFU/ml

Results revealed high bacterial contamination in both sources. The HPC measured 30 CFU/mL in spring water and over 6500 CFU/mL in the reservoir, indicating significant microbial activity. Furthermore, Total and Fecal Coliform counts in both samples exceeded 8.0 MPN/100mL, surpassing the PNSDW 2017 allowable limit of <1.1 MPN/100mL. These findings confirm microbiological failure, pointing to potential fecal contamination and rendering both water sources unsafe for drinking and possibly other uses.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The current baseline water quality of the water sources in Sitio Mampung, specifically regarding microbiological and physico-chemical parameters, revealed the following:
 - Both the spring water and water reservoir exceeded the allowable limits for Total Coliform and Fecal Coliform, indicating potential fecal contamination and failure to meet the Philippine National Standards for Drinking Water (PNSDW) 2017.
 - The spring water and water reservoir both failed the Heterotrophic Plate Count analysis, with the spring water recording 30 CFU/ml and the water reservoir exceeding 65,000 CFU/ml, surpassing the maximum allowable limit.
 - The spring water exceeded the permissible Turbidity limit, while the water reservoir met the standard.
 - Both water sources were within the acceptable limits for Total Dissolved Solids, Iron Total, Hardness Total, and pH levels according to the PNSDW 2017 standards.

2. Based on the data presented, the water sources in Sitio Mampueng, particularly the spring water and water reservoir, are non-potable and unsafe for consumption due to high levels of microbiological contaminants.
3. To improve the community's water quality and public health, the study suggests several measures, including the protection of water sources from contamination, installation of water treatment systems, and community education on the importance of water quality and safe water handling practices.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study and analysis of the results, this study presents the following recommendations:

1. The local government needs to identify the specific sources of physical, chemical, and microbiological contamination of Sitio Mampueng's water supply. This includes determining whether the contamination stems from agriculture runoff, improper waste disposal, or natural sources.
2. Research should be conducted to understand how different seasons, especially the rainy and dry seasons, affect the microbiological and chemical water parameters in Sitio Mampueng. This research should involve detailed measurements of Total Coliform, Fecal Coliform, Heterotrophic Plate Count, Turbidity, Total Dissolved Solids, Iron content, Hardness, and pH levels at different times of the year.
3. Health providers should assess the potential health risks to residents from prolonged exposure to water from both water reservoirs and spring water. This includes evaluating the likelihood of illness from microbial contaminants, especially Total and Fecal Coliforms.
4. Efforts should be made to explore various strategies for safeguarding Sitio Mampueng's water sources. This involves protecting the water sources from deforestation, land activities, and manmade practices that could lead to contamination.
5. The local sanitation and hygiene practices in Sitio Mampueng should be examined. This study could involve surveys on household sanitation facilities, waste disposal management, and hygiene habits. It should also explore the community's awareness of the quality of the water they have been consuming.
6. Expand the research to include additional water sources and factors influencing water quality in Sitio Mampueng. Investigate the impact of different water sources on overall water quality and public health. Evaluate groundwater sources, surface water, and alternative supply options, while considering factors such as land use, climate variability, and community practices.

7. Explore alternative water sources in Sitio Mampung to ensure sustainable and safe drinking water. Evaluate the feasibility and potential of options like rainwater collection, deep wells, and treatment of non-drinkable water sources.
8. Establish a health surveillance system and conduct regular assessments to monitor the impact of water quality on public health. Develop a systematic approach to monitor and collect health data related to waterborne diseases and conditions in Sitio Mampung. Track illnesses linked to water consumption and identify emerging health trends.
9. Encourage community involvement in managing and protecting water sources. Empower residents to monitor water sources, raise awareness about water conservation, and prevent contamination, fostering a sense of ownership and accountability in maintaining the safety of their water supply.
10. Research and develop affordable and effective water treatment methods tailored to the community's needs. Focus on identifying and enhancing economical water treatment technologies, such as filtration systems, solar disinfection, and simple chemical treatments, to improve water safety and public health in the community.

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